

Influence of Polyvinylpyrrolidone Synthesis

Conditions on the Formation of Gold Nanostars

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ABSTRACT

The chemical synthesis of nanomaterials has been a driving force in the advancement of nanoscience and nanotechnology. However, minor changes in the composition of the reactants and the presence of impurities can significantly alter the outcome of synthetic procedures that have been developed for a wide range of nanomaterials. The synthesis of gold nanostars (AuNSt) using polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) in N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) is no exception to this issue, as several studies have reported PVP batch dependency of the synthesis. In this context, we set to analyze commercial PVP using ^1H NMR and show that only those containing certain impurities are suitable for the synthesis of AuNSt. Following this finding, we synthesized our own PVP with the aim of replicating the synthesis conditions of commercial PVP, including its impurities. The results confirm that PVP synthesized using hydrogen peroxide as a radical initiator and ammonium hydroxide or calcium carbonate as the base, are suitable for the formation of AuNSt. Additionally, the base used in PVP synthesis was found to influence the reaction kinetics and, in turn, the shape of the resulting AuNSt. Control reactions with purified PVP show drastically decreased nanoparticle anisotropy, suggesting that the star shape is strongly dependent on the impurity profile, resulting from the selected PVP synthetic pathway. We present a solution toward customizing AuNSt shape *via* PVP synthesis and avoiding dependence on commercial PVP.

Introduction

Among a wide variety of gold nanoparticle (NP) morphologies, gold nanostars (AuNSt) have attracted significant attention,^{1,2} mainly because they typically feature sharp tips that can act as intrinsic plasmonic hotspots, for example in surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) sensing,³ photothermal therapy,⁴ and bioimaging.^{5,6} Various synthetic protocols have been developed, which allow a significant variation in shape and size, both for the core and the tips.⁷⁻¹⁰ Beyond any possible aesthetic appeal, the range of available AuNSt morphologies also allows a fine control over the main localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) band, which can be used to tailor AuNSt to a specific application.^{3,8,9} This LSPR band has been reported to originate from coupling of core and tip resonances, and thus varies with core size, as well as with the number, shape, and dimensions of the tips. The same parameters dictate the ability of AuNSt to enhance the electric near field at the tips, which is crucial for various applications.^{8,11,12}

One of the earlier methods to produce AuNSt in high yield relied on the combined use of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) and N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF). Reported by Kumar *et al.* in 2008,⁷ it was subsequently analyzed in detail and refined for its use in numerous studies.¹³⁻¹⁶ Although PVP has been repeatedly used in NP synthesis, mainly as stabilizing/shape directing agent,¹⁶ in this particular AuNSt synthesis the combination of PVP and DMF is required for both reduction and stabilization of AuNSt. The resulting AuNSt shape can be varied by changes in the pH,¹⁷ solvent,^{14,18,19} PVP concentration,⁷ seed type,¹⁴ seed to gold salt concentration ratio,^{14,20} number of growth steps,¹⁵ and growth time,¹³ thereby leading to a wide variety of morphologies and applications.²¹⁻²³

Previous studies have demonstrated that successful AuNSt synthesis requires pre-reduction of Au^{3+} (AuCl_4^-) into Au^+ (AuCl_2^-), followed by addition of Au^0 seeds, by which tips grow onto the

seeds upon reduction of Au^+ into Au^0 .¹⁴ The formation of tips and resulting star shape have been proposed to originate from the predominance of kinetic (rather than thermodynamic) effects.²⁴ For the specific case of AuNSt made with PVP, it has been proposed that PVP forms a complex with DMF^{18,25} and binds onto the gold surface through coordination of the lone pairs on the nitrogen and oxygen atoms in the pyrrolidone ring in the PVP chain.^{17,18} This binding mechanism was proposed to have a higher affinity for the {111} facets of the nanocrystal,²⁶ which would result in blocking these facets from growth and favoring growth along the [011] direction, ultimately forming spikes.⁷ However, it is well-known that nanocrystal growth can be largely affected by the presence of impurities or additives in the chemicals used during synthesis, mainly related to surfactants and other capping molecules.²⁷ PVP is no exception, and issues affecting NP synthesis have been reported, often related to specific commercial batches, which may indicate that the proposed mechanism might be incomplete and other ingredients should be considered.²⁸⁻³⁰

The synthesis of PVP is typically achieved through the free radical polymerization of N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone (VP). This process can result in the formation of 2-pyrrolidone as a primary byproduct of a secondary reaction occurring during polymerization.³¹ Literature data suggest that the performance of PVP in NP synthesis is batch dependent.^{28,29,32,33} In the wake of these reports, we propose that the currently accepted AuNSt formation mechanism in the PVP/DMF system may be incomplete and thus a detailed study is still needed. Mireles and colleagues found that silver nanoparticles are stable in solution owing to the presence of 2-pyrrolidone, only found in certain PVP batches.²⁸ Two additional studies looked at how impurities affect NP shape when using PVP in their syntheses.^{29,30} Furthermore, from the surge of reports addressing problems in PVP-related NP synthesis, we hypothesized that there might have been recent changes in the commercial production of PVP, which would affect the synthesis conditions for AuNSt formation. Therefore,

we set up to analyze the chemical composition of different commercial PVP batches and their influence on AuNSt formation. We subsequently synthesized PVP in-house, to obtain a controlled set of PVP samples and thereby assess how the PVP synthesis pathway affects AuNSt formation. As anticipated, we find that impurities, which are generated only under specific PVP synthesis conditions, are essential for PVP-mediated growth of AuNSt.

Materials and Methods

Materials

We used five different batches of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP, CAS 9003-39-8) with molecular weights (MW) of 10 kDa, referred to as PVP-1 (Merck, Sigma-Aldrich, LOT WXBC1549V), PVP-2 (Merck, Sigma-Aldrich, LOT WXBD8072V), PVP-3 (Avantor, LOT 22I274152), PVP-4 (Merck, Sigma-Aldrich, LOT WXBD8057V), and PVP-5 (Thermo Scientific, LOT M241047). The reagents 2-pyrrolidone (99%; Merck, Sigma-Aldrich, CAS 616-45-5), ammonium hydroxide (NH₄OH 28-30%; Merck, Sigma-Aldrich, CAS 1336-21-6), azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN 98%, Merck, Sigma-Aldrich, CAS 78-67-1), ethanol (EtOH absolute; Scharlau, CAS 64-17-5), chloroform (EssentQ®; Scharlau, CAS 67-66-3), copper(II) chloride (CuCl₂, 98% Thermo Scientific, CAS 7758-89-6), deuterium oxide (D₂O 99.90% D; Eurisotop, CAS 7789-20-0), diethyl ether (99%; Scharlau, CAS 60-29-7), hydrochloric acid (HCl 37 wt%; Scharlau, CAS 7647-01-0), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂ 35%; Scharlau, CAS 7722-84-1), hydrogen tetrachloroaurate (III) trihydrate (HAuCl₄·3H₂O ≥99.9%; Alfa Aesar, CAS 27988-77-8), nitric acid (HNO₃ 65%; Scharlau, CAS 7697-37-2), N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF EssentQ®; Scharlau, CAS 68-12-2), N,N-Dimethylformamide (for HPLC ≥99.9%, Merck, Sigma-Aldrich,

CAS 68-12-2) containing 0.1% LiBr (ReagentPlus®, ≥99%, Merck, Sigma-Aldrich, CAS 7550-35-8), sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃ >99.5%; Merck, Sigma-Aldrich, CAS 497-19-8), sodium citrate tribasic dihydrate (sodium citrate ≥98%; Merck, Sigma-Aldrich, CAS 6132-04-3), sodium hexametaphosphate (Merck, Sigma-Aldrich, CAS 68915-31-1) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH; Merck, Sigma-Aldrich, CAS 1310-73-2) were used as received. N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone (VP ≥99%; Merck, Sigma-Aldrich, CAS 88-12-0) was distilled before use. Milli-Q water was used in all experiments (Millipore, 18.2 MΩ cm).

Nanoparticle synthesis

All glassware, lids, and magnetic stirring bars used for synthesis were washed with aqua regia (3:1 HCl:HNO₃) and rinsed with Milli-Q water three times before use. *Warning: Aqua regia is extremely corrosive and causes severe burns. Extreme care is needed for its preparation and usage.*

Seed preparation. Citrate-capped gold NP (AuNP) seeds were prepared following the Turkevich-Frens method.^{34,35} In brief 4.25 mL of 0.1 M sodium citrate was added to 245 mL of gently boiling 0.5 mM HAuCl₄ aqueous solution under vigorous stirring. After a few seconds, the flask was removed from heat and the solution was stirred for 15 min. The final solution was left to cool down to room temperature and subsequently stored at 4 °C. The resulting citrate-capped seeds were functionalized with PVP-1 using 80 molecules of PVP per nm² of NP surface area. The selected amount of PVP was first dissolved in ethanol and then added dropwise to the citrate-capped seeds under stirring. The solution was left stirring at room temperature for 24 hours and the dispersion was centrifuged at 8960 g for 1 hour and redispersed in ethanol.¹⁴

Seeded growth of gold nanoparticles. To facilitate monitoring by UV-vis spectroscopy, experiments were performed in quartz cuvettes under stirring, using 0.2 g of PVP in 2 mL of DMF (0.1 g/mL, corresponding to 10 mM for PVP of 10 kDa). For each experiment, the corresponding PVP-DMF mixture was used as a blank. After complete PVP dissolution, 4.4 μL of a 0.126 M HAuCl_4 solution in water was injected rapidly and Au^{3+} reduction was monitored spectroscopically via changes in the charge transfer to solvent (CTTS) peak at 325 nm. Upon disappearance of the peak at 325 nm, indicating the reduction of Au^{3+} to Au^+ , 6.6 μL of PVP-functionalized gold seeds in ethanol ($[\text{Au}^0] = 6.5 \text{ mM}$) was added (leading to a ratio of Au^+ over Au^0 in the seeds of 12.8 in all experiments).

PVP synthesis

Synthesis of PVP using H_2O_2 . An aqueous solution of VP was heated to 70 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 minutes. The amounts of VP and water varied depending on the selected VP: H_2O_2 ratio, as shown in **Table 1**, while maintaining constant quantities of the other reactants. Subsequently, 2 μL of CuCl_2 0.74 mM, 3.5 μL of sodium metaphosphate 16.34 mM, and 55.2 μL H_2O_2 solution 35% w/w were added. Immediately after, 55 μL of NH_4OH 25% or 80 μL Na_2CO_3 2.36 M was added to maintain the pH at 8-9 during polymerization, and the reaction mixture was stirred overnight at 70 $^\circ\text{C}$. Following this, the aqueous fraction of the reaction crude was evaporated using a rotary evaporator at 70 $^\circ\text{C}$, adding diethyl ether during this process to help complete drying of the polymer.

Table 1. Parameters for polyvinylpyrrolidone synthesis by hydrogen peroxide for different N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone (VP) to hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) ratios.

[VP]: [H_2O_2]	VP volume (mL)	H_2O volume (mL)
1.7	0.9	5

3.3	1.9	7
5.0	2.9	10
6.6	3.9	14

Synthesis of PVP using AIBN. 320 μ L of VP and different amounts of AIBN (1.5, 8 or 38 mg) in 5 mL of water were heated at 120 °C under microwave irradiation for 20 min. Then, the aqueous fraction of the reaction crude was evaporated using a rotary evaporator at 70 °C, adding diethyl ether to improve drying. The microwave oven used in these experiments was a Biotage Initiator.

PVP Purification

PVP was purified *via* crystallization, as previously reported.²⁹ In short, PVP was dissolved in chloroform (1 mg/ mL) and precipitated using 40 mL of diethyl ether at 4 °C. The purified and supernatant fractions were separated *via* filtration and dried individually. All samples were dried using a rotary evaporator (Buchi R-210) at 50 mbar in a water bath at 65 °C. Subsequently, the solid product was left under vacuum in a Schlenk-line overnight.

Characterization

Optical Spectroscopy. Spectroscopic characterization of nanoparticles was performed on a cuvette containing the reaction mixture – prior to washing – with an Agilent UV–vis–NIR photodiode array spectrophotometer.

Transmission electron microscopy. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were collected with a JEOL JEM-1400PLUS 241 transmission electron microscope operating at 120 kV. For TEM grid preparation, AuNSt were washed by centrifugation seven times using ethanol (10-30 min, 3700 g), resuspended in ethanol and drop-cast onto a TEM grid.

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR). NMR spectra were acquired on a Bruker 500 MHz spectrometer. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm (δ) and splitting patterns are designated as “t”, triplet and “m”, multiplet. The residual signal of the deuterated solvent was adjusted to deuterium oxide 4.79 ppm.

Molecular weight determination. Polymer MW was determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC), using a Shimadzu Nexera instrument, with a refractive index detector (RID-20A, Shimadzu) and a MALS detector ($\lambda = 663.89$ nm, miniDawn, Wyatt). DMF containing 0.1% LiBr with a flow of 1.0 mL/min was used as the eluent. Separation was performed at 50 °C by using a CTO 40C column oven and Polargel-M Guard 50×7.5 mm and Polargel-M 300×7.5 mm, 8 μ m, GPC columns. Absolute MWs were determined using a dn/dc value of 0.093 mL/g,³⁶ in the Astra 8.1 software from Wyatt Technology. The sample concentration was kept at 6 mg/mL.

Results and Discussion

Because of lack of reproducibility in our standard protocol for AuNSt synthesis, we decided to test five different batches of commercial PVP, all of them with a MW of 10 kDa according to vendor’s specifications (LOT numbers provided in **Table 2**). For each sample, we monitored the reduction from Au^{3+} to Au^+ and the eventual growth of AuNSt, using the same concentrations and experimental conditions (see Materials and Methods for details). The reduction from Au^{3+} to Au^+ was monitored spectroscopically, through the disappearance of the $AuCl_4^-$ CTTS band at 325 nm, which should occur prior to the addition of Au seeds.¹⁴ We should note here that DMF in NP synthesis is not only a solvent but also a reducing agent; we found that DMF can reduce 0.275 mM Au^{3+} within 48 hours, we consider any variation on this reduction time to stem from PVP.

Table 2: Au³⁺ to Au⁺ reduction and gold nanostar (AuNSt) formation times, for commercial and in-house polyvinylpyrrolidone batches (PVPs). The time of AuNSt growth starts at the time seeds are added, once Au³⁺ has been completely reduced to Au⁺. For commercial PVPs, LOT numbers are reported in brackets. AIBN-PVPs are given a value of mg AIBN per 320 μL of N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone (VP). For NH₄OH and Na₂CO₃ PVPs including metals/complexing agents, the various VP:H₂O₂ ratios are abbreviated as r. Reduction and AuNSt formation times of 10 minutes or below are highlighted in yellow, those between 11 minutes and 1 hour are highlighted in orange, those between 1 and 24 hours in red, and samples not forming AuNSt in grey. The corresponding PVPs used in the purification are indicated with matching identifiers.

	PVP (LOT)	Au³⁺ reduction time	AuNSt growth time
commercial PVP	PVP-1 (WXBC1549V)	15 min	X
	PVP-2 (WXBD8072V) [▼]	2 min	10 min
	PVP-3 (22I274152)	25 min	24 h
	PVP-4 (WXBD8057V)	24 h	X
	PVP-5 (M241047)	24 h	X
AIBN-PVP	1.5 mg	5 h	X
	8.0 mg	5 h	X
	38 mg	5 h	X
NH₄OH-PVP	no metals	6 min	10 min
	r 1.7	1 min	5 min
	r 3.3	6 min	10 min
	r 5.0 [*]	9 min	20 min
	r 6.7	7 min	33 min
Na₂CO₃-PVP	no metals	46 min	35 min
	r 1.7	7 min	70 min
	r 3.3	22 min	40 min
	r 5.0 [*]	23 min	50 min
	r 6.7	33 min	50 min
purified PVP	PVP-2 (WXBD8072V) [▼]	3 min	15 h
	NH ₄ OH-PVP r 5.0 [*]	18 min	X
	Na ₂ CO ₃ -PVP r 5.0 [*]	40 min	X

With three older batches, PVP-(1-3), Au³⁺ was reduced into Au⁺ - within 15 minutes for PVP-1; 2 minutes for PVP-2; 25 minutes for PVP-3 (**Table 2**). For PVP-4 and PVP-5, both recently purchased PVPs, reduction was only completed after 24 hours. Upon complete reduction of Au³⁺

into Au⁺, PVP-functionalized AuNP seeds (diameter 19 nm; details in **Supplementary Information S1** and **Figure S1**) were added to the PVP/DMF/Au mixture. Nanoparticle growth was then monitored spectroscopically, until no further apparent change was observed in the LSPR band, or at the latest at 24 hours after seed addition. We aimed herewith to compare the evolution of AuNSt morphology for each PVP batch. As shown in **Figure 1A, D, E** and **S2A, D, E** reduction in the presence of PVP-1, PVP-4, and PVP-5 resulted in isotropic growth (quasi-spherical NPs), also reflected by LSPR bands at 530 nm (**Figure 1F** and **S2A, D, E**). On the other hand, PVP-3 led to the formation of AuNSt with short and rounded branches (**Figure 1C** and **S2C**) and an LSPR maximum at 570 nm (**Figure 1F** and **S2C**). AuNSt with sharp spikes were obtained when using PVP-2 (**Figure 1B** and **S2B**), in agreement with a main LSPR band around 800 and a shoulder around 550 nm nm (**Figure 1F** and **S2C**). Therefore, out of five commercial PVP batches available in our laboratory, only two of them resulted in the formation of branched NPs, and only one induced proper AuNSt growth, as expected from literature reports.^{13,14,16}

Figure 1. A-E: TEM micrographs of nanoparticles prepared using different commercial batches, PVP-1 to PVP-5. Scale bars: 50 nm; inset scale bars: 30 nm. F: Normalized extinction spectra of AuNSt prepared with PVP-(1-5). PVP LOT numbers are provided in Table 2. G: Corresponding ^1H NMR spectra of PVP-(1-5) in D_2O ; the spectrum for 2-pyrrolidone (bottom, purple) in D_2O is also shown and gray bars mark its proton resonances: ^1H NMR (500 MHz, D_2O) δ (ppm) 3.37-3.30 (t, 2H, CH_2NH), 2.26-2.19 (t, 2H, CH_2CO), 2.10-2.00 (m, 2H, $\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_2$). A color code is maintained in all panels, as labeled in G.

We thus set out to investigate potential differences in composition between the different PVP batches by means of ^1H NMR. Shown in **Figure 1G** are ^1H NMR spectra of PVP-(1-5). All spectra show overlapping signals from the polymer (see **Figure S3** for polymer signal assignment). Additionally, the NMR spectra from PVP-(1-3) which were found to reduce Au^{3+} into Au^+ , display an additional signature with sharp peaks, which is typical for small molecules. In this case, we identified a multiplet at δ 2.10-2.00, a triplet at δ 2.19-2.26, and a triplet at δ 3.30-3.37 ppm (**Figure 1F**), which accurately correspond to the 2-pyrrolidone spectrum (**Figure 1G**, purple line and gray bars). This assignment was validated by the ^1H - ^1H Correlation Spectroscopy (COSY) spectra shown in **Figure S4**, which demonstrate that the chemical shifts and H-H interactions of the

impurity in PVP-2 align perfectly with the signals of 2-pyrrolidone. This finding is supported by Mireles *et al.*, who also identified these signals as 2-pyrrolidone, only present in some PVP batches.²⁸ Interestingly, when using PVP-2 (containing the most prominent 2-pyrrolidone signature) the spikiest AuNSt were obtained, which we interpret as a trend towards spiky AuNSt with increasing 2-pyrrolidone content. On the other hand, although PVP-3 and PVP-1 display similar 2-pyrrolidone signatures, only the former could lead to branched gold NPs. It should be noted that, in a control experiment where 2-pyrrolidone was introduced to the PVP-1 solution, neither reduction nor AuNSt formation were improved (**Figure S5**). This result reinforces our hypothesis that the AuNSt formation mechanism is complex and may depend on multiple compounds formed during PVP synthesis.

To evaluate the effect of the PVP synthesis pathway on AuNSt formation, we set out to synthesize our own PVP, using two primary initiators: hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN).³¹ Both methods are based on radical polymerization but differ in activation mechanisms and reaction conditions. In the synthesis of PVP using H_2O_2 in water, VP acts as the initial monomer and H_2O_2 as a radical initiator, as shown in **Scheme 1**. H_2O_2 is a relatively unstable molecule, which can decompose to produce hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$) upon activation. These highly reactive radicals initiate the reaction by attacking the vinyl double bond in VP, forming a radical on the molecule. This second radical subsequently reacts with the double bond of another molecule and the process is repeated to eventually form long PVP polymer chains. Polymerization continues until all free radicals are consumed or neutralized.

Scheme 1. Reaction pathway to form polyvinylpyrrolidone. The mechanism is depicted below, showing intermediate steps and reactive species involved, VP stands for N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone.

The efficacy of this polymerization process is however heavily influenced by reaction conditions. Factors such as temperature, pH, and catalyst play crucial roles in the reaction. Additionally, the ratio of VP to H_2O_2 has a considerable impact on the molecular weight of the polymer. We studied the effect of each of these factors to better understand their influence on polymerization. It should be noted that, the optimal conditions for AuNSt synthesis might not be ideal for other PVP applications. As PVP is usually obtained commercially and used for a wide array of applications,³⁷⁻⁴² commercial requirements might not overlap with the best performance in NP synthesis. In the present study, we set out to find appropriate polymerization parameters for AuNSt growth. For the different PVP preparations, we analyzed the degree of polymerization *via* ^1H NMR (**Figure 2**). Taking into consideration that AuNSt synthesis worked best when using

PVP-2, we take its characteristic ^1H NMR signals to guide our PVP synthesis (black lines in **Figure 2**).

Figure 2. ^1H NMR spectra of the crude products obtained from PVP synthesis with H_2O_2 . A: influence of base (see labels) B: Influence of metals and complexing agents (see labels). C: NH_4OH -PVP at different VP: H_2O_2 ratios (see labels). D: Na_2CO_3 -PVP at different VP: H_2O_2 ratios (see labels).

Significant differences were noted in the NMR spectra for PVP synthesized using different bases and a control experiment without base. Maintaining an alkaline pH (around 9) during PVP synthesis is essential because it facilitates the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide, thereby generating the radicals required to initiate and propagate polymerization. We illustrate in **Figure 2A** the effect of different bases on the degree of PVP polymerization under four different synthesis conditions, represented as: no base, NH_4OH , Na_2CO_3 , and NaOH. In those cases where NH_4OH

or Na_2CO_3 were used as the base, characteristic signals of PVP were identified through broad peaks (e.g., 3.39 – 2.94 and 1.83 – 1.40 ppm; see **Figure S3** for PVP peaks assignment). However, the intensity of these signals was low compared to predominant signals, which correspond to short polymer chains, suggesting partial polymerization. In contrast, in the experiments performed without a base or with NaOH, only signals from short polymer chains are observed, with no evidence of longer polymers, indicating unfavorable conditions for polymerization. It is important to note that no traces of monomer were detected in any of these syntheses (**Figure 2A**). This is evidenced by the disappearance of the characteristic vinyl proton signals of VP, such as the signal at 4.42 – 4.25 ppm, in the NMR spectra of the synthesized samples (see ^1H NMR spectrum of VP in **Figure S6**). This confirms the complete reaction of the starting material. The obtained samples showed a gel-like (not powder) consistency (**Figure S7A-D**) further indicating failed or partial polymerization. These results demonstrate that, although reactions using Na_2CO_3 and NH_4OH were not fully optimized, the presence of PVP signals, albeit weak, indicate that these bases enhance VP polymerization, thus representing a promising starting point for optimizing reaction conditions.

To optimize PVP synthesis, we explored the use of catalysts, such as metal salts that may assist H_2O_2 decomposition into reactive species and subsequent polymerization. Additionally, complexing agents were added to control catalytic activity. We selected NH_4OH and Na_2CO_3 as bases because of their demonstrated efficacy (previous paragraph and **Figure 2A**), in a molar ratio of $\text{VP}:\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = 3.3$. CuCl_2 and sodium metaphosphate were used as metal salt and complexing agent, respectively. We summarize in **Figure 2B** the effect of catalysts on polymer synthesis, by comparing ^1H NMR spectra for reactions with and without catalysts. We observed that, whereas the addition of metals and complexing agents results in complete monomer to polymer conversion, reactions without metal salt show significantly lower yields under equivalent conditions and

reaction times. These results highlight the important role of metal catalysts to achieve complete polymerization. The difference is also evident in the appearance of PVP, crystallizing into a white powder in the presence of metals/complexing agents (**Figure S7F,J**) but acquiring a gelatinous texture without them (**Figure S7B,C**). We additionally note that the corresponding spectra closely match those for commercial PVP-2, including signals corresponding to a major impurity formed as the byproduct of a secondary oxidation process, resulting in the formation of 2-pyrrolidone (**Figure S8**). We finally investigated the influence of VP:H₂O₂ molar ratio on the degree of polymerization and the MW of the obtained PVP. ¹H NMR spectra are shown in **Figure 2** for syntheses carried out at different molar ratios, with NH₄OH (**Figure 2C**) and Na₂CO₃ (**Figure 2D**). According to the spectra, polymerization was achieved at all ratios, resulting in powder-like PVP (**Figure S7E-L**). The corresponding MWs were measured by GPC in DMF and the results are summarized in **Table S1**. Polymerization with NH₄OH resulted in NH₄OH-PVP with MW of 22.3, 33.7, 43.8, and 73.0 kDa, for VP:H₂O₂ ratios of 1.7, 3.3, 5.0 and 6.7, respectively. On the other hand, the MW for Na₂CO₃-PVP prepared with the same ratios were 10.6, 22.6, 26.6, and 46.6 kDa. We thus conclude that polymerization with NH₄OH consistently results in PVP with higher MW, compared to those using Na₂CO₃, and by tuning the VP:H₂O₂ molar ratio the MW can be varied over a wide range.

To evaluate whether the synthetic method affects Au³⁺ reduction and NP formation, we additionally synthesized PVP using AIBN as initiator. As previously discussed, the basic polymerization mechanism scheme remains the same, but the activation method differs. AIBN is thermally activated, thus requiring high temperature, whereas the efficacy of H₂O₂ is influenced by pH and by the presence of catalysts, in addition to temperature. We performed PVP polymerization with AIBN in a microwave oven because it provides higher energy and shorter

reaction times. Polymerization was achieved at three different amounts of AIBN (1.5, 8.0 or 38 mg) per 320 μL of VP (**Figure 3A**). In all cases, 2-pyrrolidone was also identified by the characteristic signature in the ^1H NMR spectra (**Figure 3A**). We conclude from this experiment that both polymerization with H_2O_2 , using NH_4OH and Na_2CO_3 as bases along with additional catalysts, and polymerization with AIBN in a microwave oven, result in complete PVP polymerization. In both cases, 2-pyrrolidone was obtained as a byproduct, which was also found to be present in some commercial PVP batches, PVP-(1-3).

Figure 3: Synthesis of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) with azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN), named AIBN-PVP, and their performance in gold nanoparticle (AuNP) synthesis. **A:** ^1H NMR spectra in D_2O of PVP made with 1.5, 8.0, and 38 mg of AIBN per 320 μL of N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone (see labels). **B:** UV-visible extinction spectra of AuNPs obtained using all three AIBN-PVP batches, prepared with 1.5, 8.0, and 38 mg AIBN; **C-E:** Representative TEM images of AuNPs formed upon seed addition for (C) 1.5 mg AIBN, (D) 8.0 mg AIBN, and (E) 8 mg AIBN, scale bars in main images correspond to 300 nm, and 100 nm in insets. A color code is maintained in all panels as labeled in A.

Upon successful PVP synthesis, we tested AuNSt formation according to the same protocol as previously used for commercial PVP. In all cases, the corresponding PVP/DMF mixture was used as a blank. As shown in **Figure 3B-E**, AIBN-PVP failed to yield AuNSt under any of the selected synthesis conditions. Interestingly, reduction was relatively fast at around 5 hours (**Table 2**), but no anisotropy was found in the resulting AuNPs (**Figure 3C-E**). This is interesting because, even though AIBN-PVP contained 2-pyrrolidone, it failed to form AuNSt, again suggesting (as previously seen by adding 2-pyrrolidone to commercial PVP; **Figure S5**), that the mere presence of 2-pyrrolidone is insufficient to drive AuNSt formation.

Moving to PVPs polymerized with hydrogen peroxide as initiator, we next tested AuNSt formation with NH_4OH -PVP (no metal) and Na_2CO_3 -PVP (no metal), *i.e.*, without addition of metals/complexing agents (**Figure S9**). The former was found to reduce Au^{3+} more rapidly – within six minutes – than the latter, which took 46 minutes (**Table 2**). In both cases, AuNSt were obtained, with Na_2CO_3 -PVP (no metal) yielding shorter spikes (**Figure S9A**) and an LSPR maximum at 590 nm (**Figure S9C**). However, the use of NH_4OH -PVP (no metal) resulted in AuNSt with longer and pointier spikes (**Figure S9B**) and a UV-vis spectrum featuring an LSPR maximum at 770 nm and a shoulder at 570 nm (**Figure S9C**). Considering that PVP polymerization was incomplete in the absence of metal/complexing agent, it is interesting that AuNSt were obtained. This suggests the influence of other compounds formed during these specific syntheses, assisting AuNSt formation.

We next considered AuNSt formation with Na_2CO_3 -PVP and NH_4OH -PVP, synthesized in the presence of metals/complexing agents, in which case polymerization was complete, as discussed above. For these PVP samples, reduction kinetics and AuNSt morphology followed the same

pattern as for those without metals/complexing agents. Au³⁺ reduction was also considerably faster for NH₄OH-PVP than for Na₂CO₃-PVP, with reduction times as short as one minute (**Table 2**). For both Na₂CO₃-PVP and NH₄OH-PVP, the reduction time increased with increasing VP:H₂O₂ ratio, indicating a decrease in reactivity (**Table 2**). All NH₄OH-PVP and Na₂CO₃-PVPs consistently formed stars, as shown in **Figure 4** with repeated measurements given in **Figures S10** and **S11**, respectively. A comparison of this result with AIBN-PVP, which did not form AuNSt, indicates that polymerization in the presence of H₂O₂ may be required for AuNSt formation.

Figure 4. TEM images (A-H) of AuNSt synthesized using in-house PVP, prepared with Na_2CO_3 (A-D) and NH_4OH (E-H) as the base. Reactions were run with different VP: H_2O_2 molar ratios of: 1.7 (A,E), 3.3 (B,F), 5 (C,G), 6.7 (D,H). Scale bars: 100 nm; inset scale bars: 30 nm. I: Normalized extinction spectra of AuNSt prepared with NH_4OH -PVPs (various blue lines) and Na_2CO_3 -PVPs (various orange lines) at different VP: H_2O_2 ratios, as labeled. The color code is maintained in all panels.

We briefly discuss here the differences in star shape (descriptors are defined in **Figure S12A**); overall, AuNSt made with NH_4OH -PVP were larger, with tip-to tip diameters of around 60 nm for

all VP:H₂O₂ ratios, than those made with Na₂CO₃-PVP, which measured around 50 nm (**Figures 4 and S12B,E; Table S2**). Interestingly, for both types of PVP, the number of spikes decreased with increasing VP:H₂O₂ ratio, with overall more spikes for NH₄OH-PVP AuNSt (**Figures 4 and S12C,F; Table S2**). This result points toward a higher reactivity of NH₄OH-PVP, compared to Na₂CO₃-PVP, as well as a decrease of reactivity with increasing VP:H₂O₂ ratio for both PVPs. One additional difference is that NH₄OH-PVP leads to AuNSt with sharper tips (64° - 70°) whereas Na₂CO₃-PVP had shallower tips with angles between 76° and 85° (**Figures 4 and S12D,G; Table S2**). We propose that this difference in sharpness is responsible for the different extinction maxima (**Figure 4I**), as supported by previous literature.¹⁵

A plausible reason for the difference in shape between NH₄OH-PVP AuNSt and Na₂CO₃-PVP AuNSt might be that the latter has a higher contribution of thermodynamic growth because the reaction is slower (**Table 2**). A similar effect was observed by Barbosa *et al.*,¹⁴ who performed AuNSt synthesis at different temperatures and obtained AuNSt with blunter tips when prepared at higher temperature (favored thermodynamic growth).²⁴ We found that reactivity decreased as a function of VP:H₂O₂ ratio for both bases, meaning reduction and AuNSt formation time tended to increase with higher VP:H₂O₂ ratios (**Table 2**). The VP:H₂O₂ ratio changes the MW (**Figure 2C, D**), but may also influence the amount of secondary products generated. But if we compare NH₄OH-PVP with VP:H₂O₂ ratio 1.7 and Na₂CO₃-PVP with VP:H₂O₂ ratio 3.3, both having similar MW (22.3 and 22.6 kDa, respectively, **Table S1**), we still find different reduction times and AuNSt resembling those obtained from the respective same base, rather than with different base but the same MW (**Figure 4B,E**). Interestingly, both of these PVPs are close in MW to the actual MW of PVP-2, with a nominal MW of 10 kDa but a measured MW of 18 kDa (**Table S1**). Although PVP of 10 kDa^{13,18,43} is typically used for AuNSt synthesis, also 25 kDa,¹⁵ 40 kDa,^{14,29}

and up to 58 kDa⁴⁴ PVP have been reported. The majority of our synthesized PVPs fall within this range of MW, except for the highest MW of NH₄OH-PVP, 73.0 kDa (**Table S1**). Interestingly, all of our PVPs produced AuNSt regardless of their MW.

Therefore, we propose that MW is not a major factor influencing reactivity and AuNSt shape, in agreement with previous studies.^{7,14} It should be mentioned however, that Li *et al.* obtained silver nanowires with different shapes when using PVP of different MW.⁴⁵ Overall, our results indicate that reduction kinetics and AuNSt shape are dictated by an intricate interplay of components, largely stemming from PVP synthesis conditions. Overall, NH₄OH-PVP produced pointed stars regardless of the VP:H₂O₂ ratio and Na₂CO₃-PVP stars with rounded tip regardless of the VP:H₂O₂ ratio.

Aiming at further understanding the mechanism of Au³⁺ reduction and AuNSt formation, we attempted to separate the effects of PVP itself from that of any impurities. We thus carried out the purification of three PVP samples: PVP-2 (best commercial PVP for AuNSt synthesis), NH₄OH-PVP, and Na₂CO₃-PVP, in both cases using a VP:H₂O₂ ratio of 5.0. The samples were purified *via* crystallization in chloroform and precipitation with diethyl ether. Both purified PVP and the liquid fraction were dried and analyzed by ¹H NMR. Comparison with the crude product demonstrates successful removal of impurities from the polymer, as shown by ¹H NMR and COSY (**Figures 5A-C and S13**). The concentrations of impurities in PVP were 8.2, 5.8, and 4.3 weight percent, for PVP-2, NH₄OH-PVP, and Na₂CO₃-PVP, respectively. Subsequently, the purified PVP samples were tested for AuNSt formation in DMF (**Figure 5D-F**). From the data in **Figures 5A-C and S13**, we can see those impurities (the most prominent signal being that of 2-pyrrolidone) are present in the crude PVP (top spectra in **Figure 5A-C and S13**) and in the impurity fraction (bottom spectra in **Figures 5A-C and S13**). These signals are absent in purified PVP (middle spectra in **Figures**

5A-C and S13) in PVP-2 (**Figure 5A**), NH₄OH-PVP (**Figure 5B**), and Na₂CO₃-PVP (**Figure 5C**). Interestingly, for PVP synthesized in-house (**Figure 5B,C**) a second impurity can be seen (approximately 10% of the impurity), which has a similar structure to that of 2-pyrrolidone. However, as it is not present in PVP-2 (nor in other commercial PVPs), we propose that it does not contribute to AuNSt formation.

Figure 5. ^1H NMR spectra of purified PVP and resulting AuNP morphology. A-C: ^1H NMR spectra of unpurified PVP (top), purified PVP (middle), and impurity (bottom) for PVP-2 (A), NH_4OH -PVP (B), and Na_2CO_3 -PVP (C). D-F: TEM images of AuNPs obtained from purified PVP-2 (D), purified NH_4OH -PVP (E), and purified Na_2CO_3 -PVP (F). G: Extinction spectra of AuNPs made with purified PVP samples (as labeled).

Following purification, the various PVP samples retained the ability to reduce Au^{3+} to Au^+ , albeit at a slower rate than before purification: PVP-2 completed the reduction in 3 minutes, NH_4OH -PVP in 18 minutes, and Na_2CO_3 -PVP in 40 minutes (**Table 2**). This is an interesting finding because it suggests that pre-reduction may stem from the PVP chain itself (or the PVP / DMF mixture), with a minor contribution from impurities. From the TEM images in **Figure 5D-F** and the UV-vis spectra in **Figure 5G**, we see that AuNSt formation is drastically inhibited when using purified PVP-2, NH_4OH -PVP, and Na_2CO_3 -PVP. In the case of purified Na_2CO_3 -PVP, agglomeration was observed, which may hint toward some effect of PVP impurities on NP stability, as previously reported for silver nanoparticles by Mireles *et al.*²⁸ Our results agree with previous investigations suggesting that PVP-mediated formation of silver NPs and AuNSt cannot be carried out with purified PVP.^{29,30}

Disclosing the nature of the impurity responsible for AuNSt formation would require a comprehensive chemical analysis of the product. For example, hydrazine can form in the presence of ammonium (or ammonium hydroxide) and hydrogen peroxide, as in the case of PVP made with H_2O_2 and NH_3 (or NH_4OH), has been suggested as a potential impurity leading to the formation of anisotropic AuNPs.²⁹ Our results on AuNSt prepared with NH_4OH -PVP might support this hypothesis. However, AuNSt were also obtained when using Na_2CO_3 -PVP, where hydrazine does not form, suggesting that the mechanism behind AuNSt formation may be more complex, as previously suggested.²⁹ On the other hand, we have repeatedly shown that 2-pyrrolidone does not appear to be a key player in the formation of AuNSt. However, we emphasize that our approach provides a reliable method for the reproducible production of AuNSt using PVP, thus overcoming the dependence on commercial PVP with large batch-to-batch variability. This work can also

enable further development of bottom-up approaches using PVP as shape-directing reagent, such as *in-situ* growth approaches.^{46,47}

Conclusions

By synthesizing PVP in-house, we have demonstrated that the shape of AuNSts made via the PVP/DMF method is largely affected by specific reaction conditions used during PVP synthesis, along with sub-products generated during PVP synthesis. Purification of PVP revealed that the PVP backbone primarily contributes to the pre-reduction process, whereas the anisotropic shapes of AuNSt are largely influenced by impurities present within the PVP samples. More specifically, we find that pre-reduction with AIBN-PVP (5 hours) is significantly slower than that using PVP polymerized with H₂O₂ (30 minutes or faster). Furthermore, use of AIBN-PVP resulted in the formation of spherical NPs, whereas PVP prepared with H₂O₂ resulted in AuNSt. In addition, we find that the base used during the polymerization reaction with H₂O₂ influences the shape of the resulting AuNSt. PVP made with NH₄OH leads to AuNSt with sharper tips than those made with Na₂CO₃-PVP. Therefore, we hypothesize that specific impurities, which arise under polymerization with hydrogen peroxide, are crucial for inducing anisotropy in AuNSt. This finding suggests that the shape of AuNSt can be tailored by controlling the polymerization process.

Our in-house PVP synthesis provides a more consistent and effective alternative to commercial PVP, which shows variable performance. It is worth noting that older batches of commercial PVP proved to be more effective than more recent ones, potentially indicating a modification in the production protocol for commercial PVP. The inconsistency in the performance of different commercial PVP batches highlights the need for precise LOT number reporting in NP research. This would guarantee reproducibility and enable the identification of the most suitable PVP for

specific synthesis applications. The mechanism of star formation using PVP in DMF is complex and not yet fully understood. We related here AuNSt formation to the PVP synthesis process and the impurities formed along with it, but such impurities are yet to be identified.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Additional experimental details, including photographs of synthetic products. (file type, PDF)

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Author Contributions

‡ M.W. and A.H.-R. contributed equally. M.W., A.H.-R. and L.M.L.-M. designed experiments. M.W. performed nanoparticle synthesis and analysis, A.H.-R. performed polymer synthesis and analysis. E.V.-S. and I.A.-S. performed GPC measurements. M.W., A.H.-R. and L.M.L.-M. wrote the paper. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

NOTES

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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ABBREVIATIONS

PVP, polyvinylpyrrolidone; VP, N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone; AuNSt, gold nanostar; NP, nanoparticle; AuNP, gold nanoparticle; GPC, gel permeation chromatography; MW, molecular weight; UV, ultraviolet; IR, infrared; vis, visible; AIBN, azobisisobutyronitrile; COSY, ¹H-¹H Correlation Spectroscopy; ¹H NMR, proton nuclear magnetic resonance; TEM, transmission electron microscopy; CTTS, charge transfer to solvent; LSPR, localized surface plasmon resonance; DMF, N,N-dimethylformamide

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